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Social Status of Women as depicted in the Abhijñāna-śākuntalam of Kālidāsa in context to present Indian Society

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Abstract:

Over the centuries woman has suffered her dignity and due respect in the society. It may be due to she is physically weaker than man or herself discipline of not reacting vigorously against violence. India is a spiritually developed country, where ethics have been considered as the binding principles of religion, law and social traditions. In Smriti Shastras also a due and equitable social status has been given to woman, on the basis of ethics and spirituality. Although social principles ordained in the Smriti Shastras have been the mandatory to be followed in the society, still neglecting the directive principles people have ignored the due and equitable status of the women in the past. Kālidāsa being more a seer/ ṛṣi than a merely poet has portrayed the neglecting status of women in the society. Ironically he has criticized the assaulting attitude of man towards his female counterpart.

Keywords: Kālidāsa, society, women, Shankuntala, Dushyanta, caste, marriage, tirtha, human rights, violence.

Indecent Representation of Woman:

In the society past or present women are often represented indecently depicting the figure or form of a woman in such a way that it has the effect of being indecent or derogatory or is likely to deprave or affect public morality. Poet Kālidāsa in his Shakuntala ironically cites some of such instances to analyze and to criticize how the women are often represented indecently and maliciously.

After being unrecognized by her husband Dushyanta, Shakuntala tries to present some evidences to uphold that there was wedlock between she and Dushyanta and she is the wife of later. But due to losing her finger ring at Shakra Tirtha, she could not do so. Then Dushyanta very shamefully represents Shakuntala as:

*strīnāmaśikṣitapaṭutvamamānuṣīṣu saṃdrśyate
kimuta yāḥ pratibodhavatyah /
prāgantariḥsagamanātkhamapatyajāta-
manyairdvijaiḥ parabhr̥tāḥ kila poṣayanti /¹*

The untaught cunning is observed of females (even) in those that are not of the humane race, *i.e.* even in animals, how much more (of those) who are endowed with reason (*i.e.* of women). The female cuckoos, as is well known allow their own offspring to be reared by other birds, before soaring in their sky.

*evamādibhirātmakāryanivartinīnāmanṛta-
mayavānmadhurābhirākṛṣyante viṣayiṇaḥ /²*

By such sweet words as these are voluptuaries allured by women repenting of their own words.

These insulting words aiming not only to Shakuntala but to the entire class of women are uttered by a king who has been delegated to protect the rights and dignity of his subjects.

1 Abhijñānaśākuntalam, 5/22

2 *ibid*, 5, page. 328

Kālidāsa has presented these examples how a helpless woman is often delineated disgracefully in the society. More or less Kālidāsa with these instances tries to bring to the notice of adjudicators about the necessity of enforcement of the laws to prevent such malicious behavior.

In the contemporary society to prevent these indecent representations of woman, an act called INDECENT REPRESENTATION OF WOMEN (PROHEBITION) ACT, 1987 has been laid down. The act came into force on the 2nd October, 1987. Later The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Amendment Bill, 2012 was introduced in the Rajya Sabha on December 13, 2012 by the then Minister of State (Independent), Women and Child Development, Smt Krishna Tirath. The Bill seeks to amend the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986, which prohibits indecent representation of women through advertisements or publications, writings and paintings (primarily the print media). The amendment bill seeks to widen the scope of the Act to cover all forms of communication that represents woman indecently.

Violence against woman:

Sadly, women in India and the rest of the world also have faced significant violations of their human rights for centuries. From rape and domestic violence to forced labor and denial of educational opportunities, the struggle for rights and empowerment is a daunting (demoralizing) one for Indian women. In the world's second-largest country, hundreds of millions of women are still affected by some of these issues. Women's rights are vital to the success and growth of developing nations, making projects that empower Indian women vital to the well-being of the entire country.

Violence against women (VAW), also known as gender-based violence and sexual and gender-based violence are violent acts primarily or exclusively committed against women and girls. Often considered a form of hate crime, this type of violence is gender-based, meaning that the acts of violence are committed against women and girls expressly because they are female.

The social tradition in India is that a female has to live with his husband or in laws after marriage. Manu safeguard the female class has framed certain rules to support utmost safety and security to them. He has ordained

*pitā rakṣati kaumāre bhartā rakṣati yauvane /
putro rakṣati vārdhake na strī svātantryamarhati* //³

In childhood, a woman is protected by her father in childhood, by her husband in youth and by her sons in old age. A woman should never be left alone to fend for herself.

But sometimes after marriage a wife is deserted by her husband and becomes helpless. To prevent such helplessness of a lady, Kālidāsa has critically presented the vulnerability of a woman when Shakuntala was deserted by Dushyanta:

kiṃ cātra bhavatī mayā pariṇītapūrvā ?

(Is this lady married by me earlier ?)

*vyapadeśamāvilayituṃ kimihase janamimaṃ ca pātay-
itum /*

kulaṅkaṣeva sindhuḥ prasannamambhastāṭataruṃ ca /⁴

Why sleekest thou to sully the royal title (race, family) and to ruin this person (myself), as a stream that carries away its own banks (disturbs) the clear water (and over turns) the tree on its margine ? (Translated by Moniur Williams, Pub. Harward College Library)

³ Manusmṛtiḥ, 9.3

⁴ Abhijñānaśākuntalam, 5.21

In contemporary society desertion is deemed to be a domestic violence according to recent law. The World Conference on Human Rights, held in Vienna, Austria, in 1993, and the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women in the same year, concluded that civil society and governments have acknowledged that domestic violence is a public health policy and human rights concern. The Violence Against Women Act was developed and passed as a result of extensive grassroots efforts in the late 1980s and early 1990s, with advocates and professionals from the battered women's movement, sexual assault advocates, victim services field, law enforcement agencies, prosecutors' offices, the courts, and the private bar urging Congress to adopt significant legislation to address domestic and sexual violence.

Any type of violence is illegal. Laws about violence against women give additional support to women and families affected by violence. The most significant laws related to violence against women are the Violence against Women Act and the Family Violence Prevention and Services Act (FVPSA). Learn more about your protection under each of these laws.

Gender biased discrimination vs Right to Equality

King Dushyanta inquires before Priyamvada – I wish to know this about your friend – is the vow of an ascetic, which obstructs the influence of love to be observed by her until she is given away (in marriage) or will she, forever, live with the females of the deer, beloved by her on account of having similar eyes?

Priyamvada answered to the queries raised by King Dushyanta – Honoured Sir, This person, Shakuntala, is dependent upon another even in the practice of religious rights.

It is her father's resolve, however, to marry her to a suitable husband.

The conversation, between Dushyanta and Priyambada, implicit that taking a major decision on the self, whether to marry or not, was not a right of a woman in the contemporary society of Kalidasa.

Article 14 in The Constitution of India 1949 reads that:

The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth.

The Constitution of India guarantees the Right to Equality through the article 14 to 18 of the Indian Constitution. Article 14 outlaws discrimination in a general way and guarantees equality before the Law to all the Citizens, irrespective of caste, creed, religion, sex, regions, or sex etc. The Equality of Opportunity, Non-discrimination, and Abolition of Titles in general lives amongst the Citizens of India are absolute and constitutionally qualified in it.

Here there is a controversy that a long established tradition in India that the marriage of son or daughter was an obligatory right of the parents but neither of the bride nor of the groom.

However in India there are Eight Types of Marriages according to the ancient Indian texts like Manusmriti. These are Bráhma, Daiva, Ársha, Prájápatya, Asura, Gándharva, Rákshasa, and Paisácha. In the tradition of Bráhma marriage there may not be the right of choosing own life partner. But Gándharva type of marriage, there was a freedom of exercising the rights of choosing one's own partner. In exercising this right Shakunta marries to Dushyanta and on the tradition of

Gándharva type of marriage, and her father Maharshi Kanva approves it later. King Dushyanta justifies the prevailing law of Gándharva type of marriage, as he tells:

*gāndharveṇa vivāhena bahvyo rājarsikanyakāḥ /
śrūyante pariṇītāstāḥ pitṛbhiścābhinanditāḥ* ⁵

In India there are some major acts to safeguard the humanitarian rights of women and to eliminate exploitation against females. These are:

The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006

According to the International Research Centre for Women, almost 47 percent of girls are married before the age of 18. Currently, India ranks 13 in the world when it comes to child marriages. Since child marriage has been steeped into the Indian culture and tradition since centuries, it has been tough eliminating it.

The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act was made effective in 2007. This act defines child marriage as a marriage where the groom or the bride are underage, that is, the bride is under 18 years of age or the boy is younger than 21 years. Parents trying to marry underage girls are subject to action under this law. Since the law makes these marriages illegal, it acts as a major deterrent.

Special Marriage Act, 1954

The objectives of this act are to provide – a special form of marriage in certain cases, provide for registration of certain marriages and, to provide for divorce. In a country like India and with the diverse religions and cast, when people from different faiths and caste chose to get married they do it under the Special Marriage Act.

⁵ ibid.3.20

It is not applicable to the state of Jammu and Kashmir and also extends to intending spouses who are Indian nationals and living abroad.

Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961

According to this act, taking or giving of dowry at the time of the marriage to the bride or the bridegroom and their family is to be penalized. Dowry system, giving and taking of dowry, is a norm in India. Dowry is often asked of the bride and her family by the groom and his family. The system has taken strong roots because women after marriage move in with their spouse and in-laws. Also, over the centuries, the lack for economic independence of women and the taboo towards divorce has resulted in bride burning. When demands for dowry even after marriage are not met by the girl's families, many women are tortured, beaten and even burnt. It is one of the major challenges that our society is grappling with. Women openly complaining about it have helped to spread the word and encourage other women to take a stand.

Indian Divorce Act, 1969

The Indian Divorce Act allows the dissolution of marriage, mutual consent, and nullity of marriage, judicial separation and restitution of conjugal rights. Family Courts are established to file, hear, and dispose of such cases.

Maternity Benefit Act, 1961

This act regulates the employment of women and maternity benefits mandated by law. It states that a woman employee who has worked in an organization for a period of at least 80 days during the 12 months preceding the date of her expected delivery is entitled to receive maternity benefits,

which includes maternity leave, nursing breaks, medical allowance, etc.

Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971

The Act came into effect into 1972, was amended in 1975 and 2002. The aim of the Act is to reduce the occurrence of illegal abortion and consequent maternal mortality and morbidity.

It clearly states the conditions under which a pregnancy can be ended or aborted and specifies the persons qualified to conduct the same.

Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013

To ensure women's safety at workplace, this Act seeks to protect them from sexual harassment at their place of work. Thirty-six percent of Indian companies and 25 percent among MNC's are not complaint with the Sexual Harassment Act according to a FICCI-EY November 2015 report.

Sexual harassment at workplace also includes – the use of language with sexual overtones, invasion of private space with a male colleague hovering too close for comfort, subtle touches and innuendoes.

National Commission for Women Act, 1990

The National Commission for Women (NCW) is a statutory body of the Government of India, established in January 1992. Lalitha Kumaramangalam was appointed its Chairperson in 2014.

The NCW represents the rights of women in India and provides a voice for their issues and concerns. The National Commission for Women Act aims to improve the status of women and worked for their economic empowerment.

Equal Remuneration Act, 1976

This Act prevents discrimination in terms of remuneration. It provides for payment of equal recompense to men and women workers.

It is necessary to know these and other laws in place to protect the interests of women. Only if you are aware of your rights can you fight against any injustice meted out to you at home, at the workplace, or in the society.

The statistics are always scary when it comes to the number of instances of sexual or physical violence against women in India at any given hour, day or year. There are several organizations that work towards helping women combat this constant threat of violence, and work towards making our country safer for women by initiating policy level changes and conducting awareness campaigns that aim to educate the public. Such organizations usually cover one or more of the following objectives.

- Rescue women and children from unsafe or violent environments and rehabilitate them at a safe temporary or permanent shelter.

- Provide vulnerable women with financial support or vocational training and help them become financially and socially self-reliant.

- Provide legal advice to help victims of sexual or physical violence understand her rights and initiate the judicial process to attain justice.

- Provide counseling and psychological rehabilitation.

But when a woman is in a difficult mental space, it is difficult for her to sieve through the hundreds of organizations and their contact details and reach out to the right one. Here I have attempted to make a one-stop resource page, which can serve as a directory for vulnerable women.

Azad foundation

Azad foundation focuses on women who continue in abusive relationships because of their financial dependence on their husbands. The New Delhi-based organization trains women in professions traditionally closed to them and helps them achieve financial independence.

Women undergo a half-year training course, which includes topics such as self-defence, women's rights, sexuality and reproductive rights, effective communication, grooming and most importantly, driving, which will become their future vocation. The organization's sister concern, Sakha Consulting Wings, provides employment to these women as cab drivers and thereby, safe chauffeur and car hire services to their female clients.

Set up in May 2008, the foundation has expanded its reach, and opened offices in Jaipur, Indore, and Kolkata.

Contact

Tel: +91 11 4060 1878

Email: azadfoundation@gmail.com

Website: <http://www.azadfoundation.com/>

Bharatiya Grameen Mahila Sangh

Bharatiya Grameen Mahila Sangh or BGMS (National Association of Rural Women India) was founded in 1955, and is a non-political and non-sectarian national organization with branches all over India, in 14 states and union territories. It is affiliated with the Associated Country Women of the World (ACWW), the world's largest organization for rural women, which in turn is a consultative body for such reputed international organizations such as UNESCO, WHO, and ILO.

The goal of BGMS is the welfare, and empowerment of women and children. The organization creates Mahila Mandals

(women self-help groups) across villages in its areas, for women empowerment and education.

BGMS has a short stay home for destitute women who have been ill-treated by their husbands, in-laws or other family members, and find themselves without any home. They are provided with vocational training and jobs to support themselves. Elderly women, who have nobody to look after them, can also find a home in BGMS. They are provided with food, medical care, and recreational facilities.

ICRW

International Center for Research on Women is an organization headquartered in Washington DC with regional offices in New Delhi and Mumbai. ICRW was founded with the belief that when women have opportunities to improve their lives, everyone benefits. When women earn an income and control what they do with it, their children are more likely to finish school, their families eat better, they stay healthy and the entire community thrives.

But the reality is that women face issues like violence, child marriages, lack of education and resources. ICRW carries out research that identifies barriers to economic and social stability of women and designs evidence-based plans for program designers, donors and policymakers that empower women. ICRW talks to women directly and helps their voices be heard.

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